

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This is the last issue before summer holidays are starting seriously (in the Northern hemisphere, that is) so it is time to wish you and all those who are continuously helping to make JUCS a success some nice and relaxing vacations.

Please note that not only the appearance of JUCS has been further improved but that you can now participate in a Discussion Forum, i.e. you can "annotate" any JUCS contribution, including previous annotations. This feature is something few electronic journals have to offer, so please give it a try! For more information see http://www.iicm.edu/jucs_annotations, or just "Discussion Forum" on the JUCS homepage!

Happy reading, and looking forward to a continuing stream of high quality papers,

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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